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COGNITIVE LEARNING SYSTEMS FOR PERSONALISED EDUCATION TO BUILD A STUDENT CAREER– A CASE STUDY OF IBM

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Abstract

Data analytics converts bulk of data into insights for business, healthcare, insurance and education. An upcoming development in IBM's data analytic approach towards education is cognitive learning systems. Human being and machine can communicate each other by the technologies that use Natural Language processing and Machine Language together in action. Presently, many students struggle for their education without any goals. They are unaware of marketplace requirement too. In this sense, cognitive systems should improve student education and results with a customized perception of their learning. IBM has recently pointed his service on education by its supercomputer or computing technology, IBM Watson. Such systems can research and communicate to provide expert assistants to scientists, engineers, lawyers and other professionals within a fraction of the time. It is also being used widely to assess student performance and to help educators in the classroom develop more constructive instructional practices for their students. It helps the teacher to collect attendance, marks detail and to analyse the individual student's interest based on his result. This case study will explain the power of data analytics in classroom by the teachers to assess the student's personal behaviour and the way it is used as a tool by the teachers to determine student's interest in finding the better career. Based on individual student outcome, Watson using AI will find solutions to improve quality and policy of education. Here AI technology gives tools to the teachers they need to be most effective and help learners perform at the top of their abilities like tutors, childhood vocabulary development and personalizes content for students based on mastery. Data Digital services and apps are used on learning and they help in the learning experience. This study will help to understand the way different technologies working together in predictive analytics and to prepare a report on admission, number of attendances, student dropout rate, their result analysis and their future. This study will analyse the way it is implemented on students to achieve their goals and success rate of cognitive systems in education.

Keywords: IBM Watson, AI, Machine Learning, Cognitive Systems, Data Analytics, Learning, Natural Language Processing, Predictive Analytics

1. INTRODUCTION:

The education system is very biased all over the world. The structure of the education system is common to all students, regardless of their potential and ability to learn. Each student is a common part of the class or school, with a single teacher and a specific curriculum. But each student has a distinct socio-economic background, quality and ability to understand. The system is not personalized or built on the needs of the individual student. The student scorecard may not be considered to assess his or her talent or skill during the student's admission. Because many factors may have an impact on the decline or growth of the student's grade. This statistical model would fail if, after admission, the student is driven to achieve better performance in school. Students therefore need good motivation, courage to face unforeseen challenges in life, hard work and a good curriculum in all directions of learning. Schools and colleges have a lot of student-related data to handle. The teacher's challenge here is to find out what data needs to be collected for the planning of the syllabus, the teaching policy for building a student for his future. Teachers should become educators by using advanced data analytics technology. New technologies should transform the way students now have access to educators in order to make the best use of the available technologies [1].

2. THE FUTURE OF LEARNING:

The most successful company in the world, IBM, has focused its attention on educational analytics. Better academic strategies, plans even education programs are the results of data analytics, which transforms a large part of the data into information for policymakers and educators. It converts student-data volumes to intelligence, leads to the creation of a smarter school. This emerging technology, called the cognitive learning system, is based on neuroscientific methodological innovations that develop brain-inspired computing and artificial neural network algorithms [2]. It works on perception, action and cognition of human brain. This results in the production of Watson, a cognitive supercomputing system. Watson is a question answering computer that can answer any questions posed in natural language. It's the product of IBM. This computer system was originally designed to answer questions about the 2011 Jeopardy quiz show. It was able to answer all the questions posed by legendary champions Brad Rutter and Ken Jennings and won first place with a reward of one million dollars [3].

3. EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS MORE EFFICIENT WITH ANALYTICS:

Education should consider data analytics in eight ways to build its framework in an efficient manner [4].

a. Through having smart textbooks that adjust the speed of the learner: After the exams or other evaluations, the teacher can find out whether or not the student has read the content, through looking at the results. But that time, the teacher can't help the student to improve the result. New electronic textbooks, which are devices, can therefore be used to talk and train students, depending on their learning speed, needs and potential. They can answer questions like a teacher in a classroom interaction.

b. Through personalized learning: The classroom has slow and fast learners. The teacher uses smart textbooks to measure the performance of these different categories of students and personalizes a personalized analysis for each student.

- c. By searching for pain points: Motivate students to take part in educational initiatives using sentiment analysis.
- d. By increasing the presence of the teacher: The interactive response systems adopted by the educators will make all students respond simultaneously. The feedback collected on this adoption helps to analyze the students involved and the students in difficulty in their studies.
- e. Through assessing engagement: Online learning programs and electronic textbooks help to predict student mood or interest in their studies. Long pauses can lead to the student being distracted or not following the lesson. This type of data should be obtained for predictive analysis in order to find patterns and improve accuracy.
- f. Parents informed periodically: Parents should gather information about their children about their studies; how they are engaged, which subject is difficult or easy, and their overall performance. This will help to make the most of the available resources to improve their children's success.
- g. Check for drop-out status: The education system must collect data from existing institutions on attendance level, class performance, interest, socio-economic status. Then the school will either find the drop-out rate or find solutions for the total drop-out rate.
- h. Finding cheating: If students take more time to answer an online question or quiz, then apps are available to determine plagiarism. The collected data will be used to find the amount of cheating committed by the students [4].

4. COGNITIVE LEARNING SYSTEMS:

Cognitive system is a mix of technologies that use natural language processing and machine learning. These technologies enable people and machines to interact in a natural way to enhance human expertise and cognition. In this regard IBM has developed a program of cognitive computing for learning. Here intelligence and neuroscientific knowledge work together in neurotechnology cognitive learning processes. This prototype developed by IBM includes automated cognitive learning content, cognitive tutors and cognitive learning assistants. It is designed to understand the needs of the learner, to provide constant support and personalized education for the student. Watson Teacher Advisor, an application created by IBM, can track, analyze and assess information in order to make decisions that will allow teachers to direct and encourage students to improve their teaching [2].

a. **Cognitive Learning Content:** Initially the IBM research group develops working models with likeminded institutions in order to prepare the content of the current education system. Watson, the US game-winning machine used as a cognitive computer communicates with human beings in a natural way by queries. The contents are prepared, (i) with a deep knowledge of cognitive neuroscience and cognitive process algorithms (ii) to gather feedback that evaluates informs and refreshes the contents in order to improve learning efficiency. Finally, learning content has a vision of personalized learning and of engaging learners with positive outcomes everywhere [2][5].

b. **Cognitive tutor:** It is an adaptive tutoring system that uses cognitive models to make the best recommendations when they face problems. It provided the correct interface for student communication to take the next successive steps. It also provides problem-solving skills by practice and context specific clues at the student's query. It also relies on the option of

individual issues. It collects feedback on their performance by using cognitive models to improve the direction of learning through individual attention.

Tutor works on a cognitive model using two algorithms to implement its work. They are model tracing and knowledge tracing. Through model tracing, the individual path of the participant is identified as posing complex problems and collects input to improve the accuracy of the model and provides sufficient guidance on the specific context. Throughout knowledge tracing, the tutor uses the Bayesian method to test student knowledge in order to identify the problem faced by the individual student. Both tracing approaches are used to track student learning [2].

Watson tutor, a system that uses natural language processing to direct students through review sessions to submit quiz questions on a topic asked by a teacher [6].

c. **Teaching Assistant:** IBM Watson is used in a variety of education programs. Pearson Education, Blackboard, Sesame Workshops and Apple are IBM's educational collaboration initiatives. With Pearson, IBM is able to adopt the natural language processing on electronic textbooks, a reading material that facilitates one-to-one tutoring for students. IBM and a few students has used Jill, a virtual teaching assistant, to assist students in the classroom. There is also an assistant available for parallel programming learning using IBM Watson. Specific requests or commands are answered by a software agent called an Intelligent Virtual Assistant (IVA) or an Intelligent Personal Assistant (IPA). Often chatbots are used as online chat virtual assistants [2].

d. **Watson Teacher Advisor:** Watson's Teacher Advisor is a web-based instructional planning tool created by educators. It is designed for educators to prepare presentations and schedule successful coordinated lessons. For cognitive computing systems, the Teacher Advisor tool allows teachers to make the most of their ability to reach the student's ability, based on their context. This will not displace the teacher; instead, it builds or optimizes the recursive role of the machine cognition and human cognition in learning together. Here teacher with machine algorithms are augmented and extended. This will create cognitive classrooms that studies student's behaviour, to build a model of human brain through regular interactions between educators and non-human cognitive systems. This is also driven by artificial intelligence to answer all questions asked by students over the course of the semester [2]. It will improve the ability to learn not only in the classroom, but also outside.

5. IBM WATSON EDUCATION:

For student success, learning outcomes and implementation approaches are built by IBM Watson Education Team through AI. Watson AI technology will provide educators with tools to help students make the most of their abilities [7]. Watson cognitive computing digests volumes of knowledge from text, audio, video, and other media to make the way for students to transform into a new education system. Such AI technologies should improve learner success and enable teachers to personalize learning for all types of students from pre-kindergarten to K-12 and higher education to lifelong learning [8]. AI can be used in education by these three ways [7]:

a. Based on ability of student contents are personalized: every student will get Lessons, activities and assignments based on where they are today and their ability to learn.

b. Early childhood vocabulary development program: Tablet-based vocabulary learning apps are developed to identify the additional areas of learning to enhance their future of education.

c. 1:1 AI-based tutoring for students: Each student will be tracked in order to identify his or her progress or failure to provide ideas for better solutions for the improvement of students by instructors [8].

Watson Education consists of two products: IBM Watson Element and IBM Watson Enlight. Watson Element can collect data on the educational, socioeconomic, and actions of students and allow educators to support and involve that student in the classroom. Watson Enlight highlights the academic strength, weakness of the student to plan lessons in a properly planned manner to meet the student's need for progress [6].

6. DATA COLLECTION IN IBM WATSON DISCOVERY:

IBM Watson collects unstructured data from proprietary data, public data and third-party data to retrieve information or patterns for rapid cognitive, cloud-based applications. Unstructured information is collected using queries and we'll get the answers we need. They are then integrated into our new or existing application. IBM Watson Discovery offers APIs for searching, transforming, enriching, and normalizing data. It provides security to the data collected and adds additional enrichments such as ideas, relationships, and emotions by natural language comprehension. We can also position specific questions or customer inquiries to Discovery using the IBM Watson Assistant chatbot [9].

7. IBM'S WATSON EDUCATION PARTNERS:

IBM has announced a partnership with Scholastic and Edmodo to build a strong Watson Education platform. Scholastic Go and ScienceFlix Scholastic Libraries will provide content from different media, articles, etc. in IBM Watson Education. Edmodo uses the AskMo search engine and the IBM Watson Classroom Cognitive Library to collect textbooks, test questions and lesson plans stored in the cloud to provide educational content. This will help to categorize the plans and content based on the student's grade, age and interests [6].

IBM is partnering with Sesame Workshop to develop a vocabulary app and a platform called Sesame Workshop Intelligent Play and Learning Platform [6].

It is used to create a series of cognitive devices, games and toys. IBM also has signed an agreement with Pearson and Blackboard to bring IBM's education system to colleges and universities by providing smart books as reading materials to the students [6].

IBM is also working with the Kendriya Vidyalaya Schools Network in India to support math teachers with Watson's Teacher Advisor. The AI Powered Educational Resources website helps tutors prepare lesson plans and activities with good strategies [10].

IBM is also partnered with the Government of India. AI Powered Mentor Platform developed with IBM Watson Cognitive Engine, works at Atal Tinkering Labs, with young innovators, and prepares 4,000 mentors and 6,00,000 mentees. This offers personalized support for students. This project has produced 2,500 mentors, including 300 IBMers, in association with the National Mentor of Change Mission [10].

8. PERSONALIZED LEARNING (ADAPTIVE LEARNING OR DIFFERENTIATED LEARNING):

Our educational system, supported by the universities, does not draw on the skills of graduates, which are very much required from the new job markets. Education should therefore find cognitive technology running on a lot of data, so as to allow personalized

learning to develop knowledge and expertise for students, educators and administrators. This will boost learning style, speed, and interest in education [11].

Personalized learning is a new teaching paradigm in which each student receives his or her learning plan for his or her ability and goal. The plan is designed for his knowledge ability, interest, speed and style of learning. Here, therefore, the teacher creates an up-to-date profile for each student in the school and changes it on the basis of his or her success in learning using his or her learning plan before the student fail. Based on its success rate by following the plan, each student will be given a unique schedule of learning. The student's learning program must include all events in different areas. Teachers must cooperate and inspire each student to improve their learning skills in all fields [12]. Such awareness would allow the teacher to help students achieve their potential and fear of school. This will avoid dropout rate of children. Here, one instructor can teach thirty or more students by applying analytics, even if each has different learning skills and potential. This is called one-to - one or personalized tutoring between a teacher and a student [13].

Through personalized learning, each student is personally focused and can show his mastery in his own field. Through technology, the teacher can easily keep track of every student and finds a learning gap, helps in the engaged classroom towards the achievement of the student. New technology will help to improve the relationship between educators, learners and thus the community and will provide resources to meet the specific challenges of students at different ages and stages of learning [14]. Personalized learning should make students confident in taking decisions on their own in the right direction [12].

Customized programs are made up of cognitive models by gathering input from deep interviews, surveys from schools, educators, students, families, individuals in society, and IT and marketing employees to incorporate customized digital learning [15].

The future classroom should be interactive, digitized and accessed at a remote location. More preferences for MOOCs have been shown by the students. Here students are allowed to choose a course of their choice [16].

Right technology tools mobile phones, applications, cognitive assistants, connected objects will together create a personal learning environment where students can easily meet with teachers and discuss subjects in a virtual space. Such technologies will also allow students to ask questions and answers in an interactive manner. Augmented reality and virtual reality together improve customized learning. As a result, the teacher can focus on the individual student, and the teacher can address his doubt anywhere and at any time [16]. More and more training is needed in personalized learning for educators to educate students [14].

9. WATSON EDUCATION CLASSROOM:

Watson Education Classroom is a cloud service platform that helps educators incorporate personalized learning in education. Using this, teachers can collect bulk data to understand the requirements of the student's activities. So that they can prepare for learning including a lesson plan, student schedule, progress and outcome. Cognitive programs are incorporating personalized education through this classroom. The entire learning process of the student's experience is structured through this classroom [17].

10. ACADEMIC INITIATIVES :

- IBM MobileFirst app for iOS and iPads: IBM Watson launched the first MobileFirst Education app for iPad and iOS called IBM Watson Element for Educators. It allows K-12 students and teachers to learn on a personalized basis. Teachers can, at their fingertips, have access to student's interests, attendance, learning activities and style, etc. towards success. Using this tool, teachers can get to know students beyond their academic performance [18]. There, the teacher can insert notes to the app so that the absentees can collect the information taught in the classroom. The unique feature called "spotlight" in the app, can have a special focus on the student by the teacher lets the other teacher know about the student's talent. The App will also have features such as opportunities to involve the classroom through communication, the teacher's main role is to concentrate each student's knowledge and monitor academic progress towards learning standards.
- Tabor Math: It is built to understand students' minds by the keystrokes they touch as they solve problems. It's connected with IBM Watson to help teachers understand that student's problems with the solution. This increases the student's learning outcomes by increasing the rate of understanding of subjects by 90% [19].
- Many mobile language applications help millions of students learn foreign languages on their own. They will provide adaptive learning algorithms. A recent math app trial built for children in Malawi. The students will only be able to make progress in six weeks, which will take 12 to 18 months of traditional teaching methods [13].
- IBM's Medical Minecraft game can move through the human body. Health encyclopedia is digested as input from IBM to implement this game. AI and NLP together give the student a feeling of going inside the human body and disease. Using this game, students can grasp subjects with ease [20].
- Teachers TryScience is a web site developed by IBM for teachers. 4 million teachers in the Indian Open Educational Resources Community are using STEM to get STEM-related hands-on lessons, resources, teaching strategies and other support for teaching. It is written in 9 Indian languages and covers 12 Indian states. The page also offers some opportunities for teachers to share their opinions with other educators in order to improve their practices [21].
- THINK app: It is free of charge for iPad and 10" Android tablets developed by IBM. This provides students with access to a systematic approach through a series of methods, Seeing, Mapping, Understanding, Believing and Acting (SMUBA). Here students can seek technologies and take part in different STEM systems with hands-on lessons of experience and practice [22].

The Next Generation Science Standards (NGSS) will help students study science as a fun and interesting subject. Here, teachers will have high standard materials and resources of high quality. Teachers TryScience Advanced Tools are used to update and review current K-12 science lessons more in line with NGSS using the Educators Evaluating Quality in

Instructional Products (EQuIP) rubric. Using the EQuIP process the New York Hall of Science (NYSCI) initiative, educators have revised existing lessons and updated more active, insightful lessons. The EQuIP rubric process is used by educators to continually update and refine lessons and resources on the basis of feedback and suggestions. It is also used to find the strength and weakness of every lesson [23].

IBM has created a game, Cognitoys Dinosaurs that provides answers to questions, tells bedtime stories, and plays interactive games, etc. with children [24].

Sesame Workshop: This is the cognitive learning platform; here, sesame street characters like Grover and Elmo were created to educate children on their own. Such characters should educate students to playful and age-appropriate interactions for fun and knowledge. This offers more applications, games, learning toys, etc. to engage students in enjoyable education. It also provides a vocabulary app for kindergarten children, which helps children pronounce challenging words with ease. The cognitive tutor reads the minds of students whether they are struggling to get things done and offers the right solution and advice to make things easier and make progress. Here, students are going to be busy studying in and out of classes [25].

11. CONCLUSION:

In the digital era, the transformation of life is also expected to change education. The future of children is influenced by schooling. IBM is developing better future cognitive learning methods. The complexities of current education are turned into new and innovative approaches for putting an individual on a lifelong journey. Such approaches have been continuously updated by IBM Watson, a cognitive tool which uses human input in the right direction to build a student in his career. IBM Watson Education has reached more than 2 Lakh students in different countries around the world. Watson Tutor has shown that the student performance has improved by 40% and is assessed by A / B experiment done by IBM.

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